

The Influence of Human Factors and Measurements on The Formation of Cybersickness while using Virtual Reality: Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract: Cybersickness is an impact arising from the use of virtual reality. It can be influenced by many factors, including the human factor. As virtual reality users, humans feel their movement through various sensory organs, such as sight and hearing. Many researchers have conducted studies on cybersickness caused by various human factors. This article aims to explore the concept of human factors, examine their influence on cybersickness, and review the methods used to measure them. A total of 39 out of 653 articles, taken from trusted databases and published from 2000 to May 2024, were reviewed. They were selected and sorted using the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA). The result shows that the human factors used to identify cybersickness are age, sex, congenital disease, body mass index, ethnicity, experience, and posture. The articles show supporting and opposing findings toward each other regarding human factors. Meanwhile, the measurement was generally carried out using a subjective measurement called SSQ.

Keywords: cybersickness; human factors; measurement; virtual reality.

1. Background

Virtual reality (VR) gradually provides more benefits, not only as a game¹. For example, VR-based shooting simulations have been reported to enhance self-defense skills², flight games improve aircraft operation ability³, and body anatomy-based VR games are widely used in education⁴. In sports, VR is being integrated into training programs for both professional athletes or general exercise purposes⁵⁻⁸.

With the growth adoption of VR for various activities, concerns over cybersickness have increased. Users, whether using a Head Mounted Display (HMD) or a Monitor Display (MD), may experience cybersickness symptoms, such as nausea, dizziness, disorientation, and discomfort, which can occur during or after VR exposure⁹⁻¹³. Cybersickness occurrence can be influenced by multiple factors, such as hardware/software, tasks, and human factors.

Hardware is one of the critical factors in determining the severity of cybersickness. As technology advances, hardware specifications are constantly evolving to increase

user satisfaction and achieve goals envisioned by the developer. One study examined whether a device provides comfort when being used¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The results show that cybersickness increases when using HMD, particularly if the device is too heavy or strapped tightly to the head¹⁶⁻²¹. Similarly, software also plays a significant role in user satisfaction and is another potential cause of cybersickness. Software-related factors that can contribute to cybersickness include flicker, realism, color, and scene complexity²²⁻²⁶. Additionally, blinking frequency, which is linked to cybersickness, is influenced by the screen's refresh rate, luminance, and field of view (FOV)^{27,28}.

In addition, cybersickness is closely linked to individual differences among VR users. Numerous studies have identified human factors as significant contributors to cybersickness. The severity of cybersickness differs among individuals, even when using the same VR content on the same device²⁹.

Researchers have previously examined human factors, such as age, gender, BMI, congenital diseases, posture, experience, and ethnicity, yielding various and sometimes conflicting results. While some findings align with earlier

studies, others present contradictory conclusions, highlighting the complexity of cybersickness and the need for further investigation.

Multiple studies have established correlations between postural instability and cybersickness³⁰⁻³⁴. Posture is key experimental factor, typically categorized into three basic levels: sitting, standing, and supine postures. Research reveals that sitting postures generally induce less cybersickness than standing postures³⁵⁻³⁷. Meanwhile, another study on supine posture shows that this posture can trigger more severe symptoms than sitting, even for inexperienced virtual reality users³⁸.

Accurate measurement is essential for identifying the factors contributing to cybersickness. Thus far, cybersickness can be measured using subjective and objective methods. The subjective measurements are commonly conducted using questionnaires, such as the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ)³⁹. The SSQ is typically administered during, after, or as part of mitigation efforts when using the HMD⁴⁰⁻⁴². While subjective measurements provide quick insights into a user's current condition, they are usually conducted after VR use, making it difficult to capture real-time symptoms of cybersickness⁴³. Additionally, the severity levels reported by users may vary between individuals, potentially leading to inconsistencies in the results⁴⁴.

Objective measurement can also be used to enhance the accuracy of cybersickness measurement when used alongside subjective methods. Various physiological tools are employed for objective measurement, including electrocardiography (ECG)⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹, eye movements⁵⁰, electrogastragraphy (EGG)⁵¹, electroencephalography (EEG)^{48,52-54}, galvanic skin conductance (GSC)⁴³, and respiration and hormone levels⁴⁴. These objective tools allow for real-time monitoring of physiological changes associated with cybersickness during VR exposure, whether experienced using an HMD or MD.

The objective measurement can capture dynamic physiological changes in the formation of cybersickness in each user in real-time during exposure without interfering with virtual reality⁴⁵. However, the accuracy of physiological measurement lies in the quality of each sensor, its positioning, and the user's movements³⁸.

This literature review aims to determine which human factors are most relevant to be the cause of cybersickness, how the human factor affects the occurrence of cybersickness, and what measurements shall be used to measure cybersickness caused by the human factor. This literature review also provides insight into current research findings and future research plans.

2. Research Methods

Using relevant keywords, articles were searched from Google Scholar, Science Direct, Scopus, Springer, and

IEEE. The initial search used the terms 'VR sickness,' 'cybersickness,' 'motion sickness,' 'simulator sickness,' 'virtual reality,' and 'human factors' as keywords. The range between publication periods was set from 1999 to May 2024. A total of 653 articles were obtained from the databases. Among them, 212 articles have duplicate titles and were subsequently removed. The remaining 441 articles, having no duplicate titles, were quickly reviewed based on their abstracts. Three hundred and twenty articles were excluded as their research did not include human factors as the primary focus. As a result, 121 articles were shortlisted. These 121 articles were then carefully reviewed in detail. Meanwhile, 63 articles were excluded because they are incomplete or do not sufficiently focus on human factors. The remaining 60 articles were further evaluated, and only research articles were selected. Articles categorized as literature reviews, theses, or annual reports were excluded. Finally, 39 articles meet the criteria for further in-depth and complex review. The process of selecting and sorting articles in this literature review applies to the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) stages, as seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Identification of Article Selection and Sorting.

3. Result And Discussion

A comprehensive database search identified 39 articles on human factors and their associated measurement methods. These articles were published between 2000 and May 2024. Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of the selected articles following a relevance-based screening process for the literature review.

Fig. 2: Distribution of Articles by Year

Human factors associated with cybersickness, as identified in most articles, were most frequently examined in studies conducted in 2020, with seven published articles. In contrast, studies focusing on human factors to identify cybersickness were minimal between 2000 and 2002, 2010 and 2015, and 2022, with only one article addressing this topic during each period.

From 2018 to May 2024, researchers have increasingly focused on human factors, aligning with the growing adoption of virtual reality technology. In 2021, six million virtual reality headsets were sold worldwide, totaling 16.5 million. Over the next three years, the total number of virtual reality headsets sold is projected to exceed 34 million⁵⁵).

3.1. Human Factors Affecting Cybersickness

The literature review reveals that human factors, such as gender, age, body mass index, pre-existing medical conditions, and ethnicity, are used to identify the causes of cybersickness. The distribution of these human factors examined in the studies is illustrated in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Distribution of Human Factors

Gender is most examined in research on cybersickness, accounting for 46% of the studies, followed by age at 32%. In contrast, the least examined human factor is Body Mass

Index (BMI), representing only 5% of the studies.

3.1.1. Gender

Gender, as a key demographic factor, is one of the most studied variables influencing cybersickness. Several studies indicate that women are generally more susceptible to cybersickness than men^{23,56-60}). Recent research supports these findings, confirming that women tend to develop cybersickness more quickly than men^{61,62}). Various factors contributed to this increased susceptibility, including differences in FOV^{63,64}), hormone levels⁶⁵), and sensitivity to motion sickness^{66,67}

However, some studies present contrasting findings. Research suggests that when men and women are exposed to the same conditions and performance levels, there is no significant differences in cybersickness occurrence⁶⁸⁻⁷⁶). Given these discrepancies, further research is needed to clarify the relationship between gender and cybersickness.

3.1.2. Age

Several studies have concluded that the age influences cybersickness. Research indicates that individuals aged between 18 and 40 showed a significant increase in SSQ scores compared to younger age groups⁶⁴). Additionally, older adults aged between 70 and 90 years tend to develop cybersickness more quickly than those aged 21-50 years⁷⁷⁻⁸⁴).

Children aged 12 years show the more intense symptoms of cybersickness. Children aged 4 to 10 years may start experiencing cybersickness symptoms after about an hour of using virtual reality. However, the symptoms tend to get milder as they reach the age 21⁸⁵)

However, a meta-analysis shows conflicting findings, reporting that individuals under 35 have higher total SSQ scores than older age groups⁸⁶). Similarly, a study by Godge⁸⁷) states that older users experience milder cybersickness than younger users aged between 26 and 35. Additionally, one study found that users aged 18 to 64 did not experience significant symptoms of cybersickness⁸⁸). Another study also reported similar findings, suggesting that despite age-related declines in sensorimotor abilities, cybersickness is not directly associated with age, nor is there significant habituation leading to cybersickness⁸⁹). Further research is needed to clarify these discrepancies in the literature.

3.1.3. Congenital Diseases

Another factor influencing the development of cybersickness is an individual's health condition. Factors such as fatigue, lack of sleep, intoxication, stomachache, periods of emotional stress, cold, flu, ear infection, or upper respiratory diseases can affect how quickly or slowly cybersickness develops^{26,90}). Meanwhile, more severe illnesses can accelerate the onset of cybersickness even more than mild conditions. These include multiple sclerosis, migraine, excessive stress, and myopia⁹¹⁻⁹⁴). In

addition, individuals with multiple sclerosis not only experience a higher likelihood of cybersickness while using virtual reality but may also endure its effect for up to 30 minutes after using virtual reality⁹⁵).

3.1.4. Body Massa Index (BMI)

Another factor influencing the onset of cybersickness is an individual's body mass index (BMI). Research suggests a correlation between the BMI and the oculomotor disturbance of SSQ (SSQ-O). BMI that leads to obesity causes cybersickness to occur more quickly^{66,96}. However, other studies suggest that BMI does not have a direct influence on the occurrence of cybersickness⁹⁷

3.1.5. Ethnicity

Only a few studies have explored the relationship between ethnicity and cybersickness. The first study by Silva⁹⁸ found that Caucasians and Chinese individuals exhibit different susceptibility to cybersickness, with Caucasians tolerating rotational motion for a longer duration than Chinese participants. Another study reported that Asians experienced greater disturbances in gastric activity and more severe cybersickness compared to European American and African American groups⁹⁹.

3.1.6. Posture

Unstable postures or prolonged physical activity can contribute to discomfort¹⁰⁰. Postural instability is a key factor in motion sickness, as sensory inputs—visual, auditory, and vestibular—stimulate the balance mechanisms, making it difficult for the brain to maintain an upright position.⁶⁴

The concept of postural instability arises when individuals must maintain stability while their bodies respond to VR interactions. According to the postural instability theory, cybersickness is always preceded by increased postural instability, which persists until the stability is restored. Individuals with balance disorders are more prone to developing cybersickness during VR use¹⁰⁰.

Previous research suggests that passive postures, such as sitting, may reduce the risk of cybersickness in rollercoaster video games by enhancing postural stability³⁰. One study found that cybersickness occurs more frequently when the user stands while using an HMD compared to sitting¹⁰¹. However, these findings contradict other studies suggesting that passive postures do not necessarily lower the risk of cybersickness^{12,40,102}. Research specifically exploring postures in VR settings found that all standing participants withdrew early due to cybersickness symptoms. Interestingly, sitting participants also experienced significant discomfort, suggesting that sitting may not provide much relief¹².

A review of existing literature identified 36 studies that actively considered posture as a factor in cybersickness development. This aligns with the previous findings, highlighting the importance of user posture in VR

experiences. The different user postures in VR uses are illustrated in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: User Posture

3.1.7. User Experiences

Among the 39 articles reviewed, four identify user experience as a key factor influencing the level of cybersickness severity VR use. Several studies suggest that prior gaming experience may enhance users' ability to adapt to VR environment, leading to lower levels of cybersickness^{76,91}. Individuals with greater gaming experience experienced less overall cybersickness and vestibular symptoms, but it did not significantly impact nausea or oculomotor symptoms⁷⁶. Another conflicting finding reported no significant difference in cybersickness levels between experienced and inexperienced VR users^{72,74}. These discrepancies suggest that additional factors, such as individual sensory processing abilities, cognitive adaptation, and VR design characteristics, may modulate cybersickness responses beyond more exposure.

3.2. Cybersickness Measurement

Various techniques are used to effectively measure the development of cybersickness, typically categorized into subjective and objective methods. The subjective measurement typically employs questionnaires, which provide an intuitive for users to describe their discomfort during or after VR exposure. The objective methods capture physiological changes associated with cybersickness, including postural instability and various body signals.

3.2.1. Subjective Measurement of Cybersickness

Based on the literature review of 39 research articles, SSQ is the most commonly used tool for subjective measurement of cybersickness in all of studies (table 1). The SSQ consists of 16 items, each rated on a scale from 0 to 3, reflecting the severity of the participant's symptoms. The SSQ comprises of three subscales: nausea, oculomotor, and disorientation. A higher total SSQ score indicates more severe cybersickness, with a score above 33.3 points suggesting a high level of discomfort¹⁰³.

Other researchers have also utilized the fast motion sickness scale (FMS)^{60,93} and the motion sickness

assessment questionnaire (MSAQ)⁸⁰⁾ for subjective measurement. These measurement methods were also used in conjunction with the SSQ^{80,93)}. The FMS involves participants verbally reporting their level of discomfort every minute, using a scale ranging from 0 (not painful at all) to 20 (seriously painful), based on individual criteria²⁴⁾. Additionally, the cybersickness questionnaire (CSQ), developed by Stone,¹⁰⁴⁾ is formulated to refine the SSQ by focusing specifically on symptoms directly related to cybersickness. The CSQ helps distinguish between symptoms caused by cybersickness and those stemming from other factors. The mapping of these articles and their methodology is illustrated in Figure 5

Fig. 5: Cybersickness Measurement

The article mapping in Figure 5 highlights the predominantly used of SSQ in subjective measurement. The SSQ is widely recognized as an effective tool for assessing cybersickness both before and after VR exposure.

3.2.2. Objective Measurement of Cybersickness

Subjective methods have limitations in accurately detecting cybersickness, as they depend on self-reported data and the individual experience. Those assessments can be influenced by individual differences in tolerance and adaptation to VR. To improve accuracy, objective methods can be employed. Unlike subjective approaches, the objective measurements capture physiological responses in real-time, although the outcome may not always correspond with the subjective report¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁷⁾.

Most methods of objective measurement focus on postural instability (figure 5) or electrophysiological changes^{62,73)} in the body during VR use. The literature review of 39

research articles found that only three studies employed objective measurement using galvanic skin response (GSR) as one of objective measurements. GSR, a type of electrodermal activity (EDA) measurement, assesses skin conductivity changes triggered by external stimuli. It is typically measured on the feet, wrists, or forehead. Additionally, some studies used a combination of multiple objective methods of objective measurement, including EEG to track brain responses⁶²⁾, EGG to monitor gastric disturbances⁶²⁾, and ECG to measure heart rate variability (HRV)⁶²⁾. These combined approaches offer a more comprehensive assessment of cybersickness by analyzing multiple physiological indicators.

3.3. Types of Virtual Environment

Among the 39 research articles reviewed, 28 studies focused on virtual environments in games (figure 6), making them the most commonly observed settings. This prevalence is closely linked to the rapid growth of HMD-based gaming systems, such as Oculus Rift, HTC Vive, and PlayStation VR, which offer immersive VR gaming experiences.

Additionally, VR environments involving simulators, such as driving simulators^{67,77,80,83,92,108)} or space station simulations⁸¹⁾, were examined in 7 research articles. The detailed distribution of virtual environment types is presented in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Types of the Virtual Environment

Overall, the result of the literature review that has been carried out is depicted in Table 1.

Table 1: Article Recapitulation

Authors	Factors	Measurement		Virtual Reality	Posture
		Subjective	Objective		
Mourant, and hattacheny ⁶⁷⁾	Gender	SSQ	-	Driving Simulator	Active
Kingdon et al ⁹⁷⁾	BMI	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Hakkinen et al ⁶⁴⁾	Age	SSQ	-	Movie	Active
	Gender				

Authors	Factors	Measurement		Virtual Reality	Posture
		Subjective	Objective		
Clemes, and Howarth ⁶⁵⁾	Gender	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Arns, and Cerney ⁷⁹⁾	Age	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Klosterhalfen et al ⁹⁸⁾	Ethnic	MSQ		Game	Active
Golding ⁷⁵⁾	Gender	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Knight, and Arns ⁶⁸⁾	Gender	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Park et al ⁷⁷⁾	Age	SSQ	-	Driving Simulator	Active
Brooks et al ⁸⁰⁾	Age	SSQ, MSAQ	-	Driving simulator	Active
Kim et al ⁹⁰⁾	Congenital disease	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Rebenitsch, and Owen ⁷⁸⁾	Age	SSQ		Game	Active
Arafat et al ⁹²⁾	Congenital disease	SSQ	GSR	Driving simulator	Active
Liu et al ⁸¹⁾	Age	SSQ	-	Simulated Space Station	Active
Paroz, and Potter ⁹¹⁾	Experience	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Gonçalves et al ⁵⁸⁾	Gender	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Hildebrandt et al ⁸²⁾	Age	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Melo et al ⁶⁹⁾	Gender	SSQ	-	Video 360	Active
Keshavarz et al ⁸³⁾	Age	SSQ	-	Driving Simulator	Active
Zhou et al ⁷⁰⁾	Gender	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Tychsen, and Foeller ⁸⁵⁾	Age	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Curry et al ⁷¹⁾	Gender	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Weech et al ⁷²⁾	Gender and experience	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Hendrika et al ⁷³⁾	Gender	SSQ	GSR	Game	Active
Sagnier et al ⁷⁴⁾	Gender and Experience	SSQ	-	Aircraft - manufacturing workshop	Active
Stanney et al ⁶⁶⁾	Gender	SSQ	-	Game	Passive
Petri et al ⁸⁴⁾	Age	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Wang et al ⁹⁹⁾	Ethnic	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Chang et al ⁹³⁾	Congenital disease	SSQ dan FMS	-	VR Vidio	Active
Goodge et al ¹⁰⁸⁾	Age	SSQ	-	Simulator Driving	Active
Luong et al ⁵⁹⁾	Gender	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Kourtesis et al ⁷⁶⁾	Gender and Experience	CSQ-VR	Eye Tracking	Game	Active

Authors	Factors	Measurement		Virtual Reality	Posture
		Subjective	Objective		
Christian ⁹⁴⁾	Congenital disease	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Jasper et al ⁸⁸⁾	Age	SSQ	-	Game	Active
	Gender				
Pöhlmann et al ⁶⁰⁾	Gender	FMS	-	Game	Passive
Séba et al ⁸⁹⁾	Age	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Pau et al ⁹⁵⁾	Congenital disease	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Zhang et al ⁶¹⁾	Gender	SSQ	-	Game	Active
Tian and Boulic ⁶²⁾	Gender	SSQ	EEG, EGG, ECG	Game	Passive

3.4. Research Opportunities

This study has certain limitations. The factors examined are primarily focus on human aspects, whereas hardware and software factors may also play a role in the occurrence of cybersickness during VR use.

The presence of contradictory results in cybersickness research presents opportunities for future studies. One such factors is gender, where studies have yielded inconsistent results. Some researchers suggest that women are more susceptible to cybersickness than men^{58,59,66,67,75)}, while other studies report no differences in the development of cybersickness⁶⁸⁻⁷⁴⁾. Similar discrepancy exists in research on age-related factors on cybersickness. Some studies suggest that age influences cybersickness severity, whereas recent findings suggest that respondents aged 18 to 64 do not show significant effect on the occurrence of cybersickness⁸⁸⁾.

Future research should explore human factors that have received limited attention, such as BMI, ethnicity, and congenital conditions. A particularly promising area is user posture, which has largely been examined in the context of active movements. However, passive postures remain understudied, even though many VR applications do not require significant user movement. Investigating how different postures influence cybersickness could provide valuable insights for VR content design and user experience optimization.

Additionally, user experience with VR warrants further examination. Prior studies have reported conflicting findings regarding the relationship between experience and cybersickness, indicating a need for more targeted research. Future studies should explore how factors such as BMI, ethnicity, and prior exposure to gaming influence cybersickness, particularly when comparing gamers and non-gamers. These investigations could provide a more comprehensive understanding of individual differences in

cybersickness susceptibility and inform strategies to improve VR usability.

4. Conclusion

Cybersickness is a key topic in the use of VR. The occurrence of cybersickness is influenced by various factors, including human characteristics as active users. This review aims to identify human factors contributing to cybersickness and the measurement methods used by researchers to assess its occurrence. A literature review of 39 selected articles revealed that researchers have examined several human factors related to cybersickness, including gender, age, body mass index (BMI), congenital conditions, ethnicity, and prior experience. Among these, gender is the most studied factor, followed by age. However, findings on these two factors are often contradictory, highlighting the need for further investigation. Regarding measurement methods, the SSQ is the most widely used subjective assessment for evaluating cybersickness in relation to human factors. Objective measurements, such as GSR, have been applied in only two studies, indicating a gap in the use of physiological markers for assessing cybersickness.

References

- 1) M.Kowal, A.J. Toth, C. Exton, and M.J. Campbell, "Different cognitive abilities displayed by action video gamers and non-gamers," *Comput Human Behav*, 88 255–262 (2018). doi:10.1016/j.chb.2018.07.010.
- 2) K.K.Bhagat, W.K. Liou, and C.Y. Chang, "A cost-effective interactive 3d virtual reality system applied to military live firing training," *Virtual Real*, 20 (2) 127–140 (2016). doi:10.1007/s10055-016-0284-x.
- 3) X.Liu, Y. Liu, X. Zhu, M. An, and F. Hu, "Virtual reality based navigation training for astronaut

- moving in a simulated space station,” VAMR Springer Verlag, 2016: pp. 416–423. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-39907-2_40.
- 4) G.M.N.Isabwe, M. Moxnes, M. Ristesund, and D. Woodgate, “Children’s interactions within a virtual reality environment for learning chemistry,” in: *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, Springer Verlag, 2018: pp. 221–233. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-60018-5_22.
 - 5) K.Petri, “Towards the usage of virtual reality for training in sports,” *Biomed J Sci Tech Res*, 7 (1) (2018). doi:10.26717/bjstr.2018.07.001453.
 - 6) K.Petri, S. Masik, M. Danneberg, P. Emmermacher, and K. Witte, “Possibilities to use a virtual opponent for enhancements of reactions and perception of young karate athletes,” *Int J Comput Sci Sport*, 18 (2) 20–33 (2019). doi:10.2478/ijcss-2019-0011.
 - 7) K.Petri, P. Emmermacher, M. Danneberg, S. Masik, F. Eckardt, S. Weichelt, N. Bandow, and K. Witte, “Training using virtual reality improves response behavior in karate kumite,” *Sports Engineering*, 22 (1) (2019). doi:10.1007/s12283-019-0299-0.
 - 8) K.Petri, C. Timmerevers, J. Luxemburg, P. Emmermacher, C.-D. Ohl, M. Danneberg, S. Masik, and K. Witte, “Improvement of movement execution in karate due to observational learning with a virtual reality application for smartphones-a pilot,” *Journal of Martial Arts Research*, 2 (1) (2019). doi:10.15495/ojs_25678221_21.
 - 9) L.Rebenitsch, and C. Owen, “Review on cybersickness in applications and visual displays,” *Virtual Real*, 20 (2) 101–125 (2016). doi:10.1007/s10055-016-0285-9.
 - 10) R.S.Kennedy, J. Drexler, and R.C. Kennedy, “Research in visually induced motion sickness,” *Appl Ergon*, 41 (4) 494–503 (2010). doi:10.1016/j.apergo.2009.11.006.
 - 11) P.A.Howarth, and P.J. Costello, “The occurrence of virtual simulation sickness symptoms when an hmd was used as a personal viewing system,” *Display*, 18 107–116 (1997). doi: 10.1016/S0141-9382(97)00011-5.
 - 12) O.Merhi, E. Faugloire, M. Flanagan, and T.A. Stoffregen, “Motion sickness, console video games, and head-mounted displays,” *Hum Factors*, 49 (5) 920–934 (2007). doi:10.1518/001872007X230262.
 - 13) K.M.Stanney, K.S. Hale, I. Nahmens, and R.S. Kennedy, “What to Expect from Immersive Virtual Environment Exposure: Influences of Gender, Body Mass Index, and Past Experience,” *Hum Fact*, 45 (3) 504 - 520 (2003). doi: 10.1518/hfes.45.3.504.27254
 - 14) K.Benzeroual, and R.S. Allison, “Cyber (motion) sickness in active stereoscopic 3D gaming,” in: *International Conference on 3D Imaging*, IEEE, 2013: pp. 1–7. doi:10.1109/IC3D.2013.6732090.
 - 15) J.Häkkinen, F. Ohta, and T. Kawai, “Time course of sickness symptoms with HMD viewing of 360-degree videos,” *J. Imaging Sci. Technol*, 62 (6) 1-11 (2018). doi:10.2352/J.ImagingSci.Technol.2018.62.6.060403.
 - 16) S.Sharples, S. Cobb, A. Moody, and J.R. Wilson, “Virtual reality induced symptoms and effects (vrise): comparison of head mounted display (hmd), desktop and projection display systems,” *Displays*, 29 (2) 58–69 (2008). doi:10.1016/j.displa.2007.09.005.
 - 17) B.Keshavarz, and H. Hecht, “Visually induced motion sickness and presence in videogames: The role of sound,” in: *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 2012: pp. 1763–1767. doi:10.1177/1071181312561354.
 - 18) J.Kim, W. Luu, and S. Palmisano, “Multisensory integration and the experience of scene instability, presence and cybersickness in virtual environments,” *Comput Human Behav*, 113 (2020). doi:10.1016/j.chb.2020.106484.
 - 19) R.Vlad, O. Nahorna, P. Ladret, and A. Guerin, “The influence of the visualization task on the simulator sickness symptoms - A comparative SSQ study on 3DTV and 3D immersive glasses,” in: *3DTV Vision Beyond Depth (3DTV-CON)*, IEEE (2013): pp. 1–4. doi:10.1109/3DTV.2013.6676647.
 - 20) M.S.Dennison, A.Z. Wisti, and M. D’Zmura, “Use of physiological signals to predict cybersickness,” *Displays*, 44 42–52 (2016). doi:10.1016/j.displa.2016.07.002.
 - 21) J.F.Golding, K. Doolan, A. Acharya, M. Tribak, and M.A. Gresty, “Cognitive cues and visually induced motion sickness,” *Aviat Space Environ Med*, 83 (5) 477–482 (2012). doi:10.3357/ASEM.3095.2012.
 - 22) F.Bonato, A. Bubka, S. Palmisano, D. Phillip, and G. Moreno, “Vection change exacerbates simulator sickness in virtual environments,” in: *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 2008: pp. 283–292. doi:10.1162/pres.17.3.283.
 - 23) B.K.Jaeger, and R.R. Mourant, “Comparison of simulator sickness using static and dynamic walking simulators,” in: *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, 45 (27) 1896–1900 (2001). doi:10.1177/154193120104502709.
 - 24) B.Keshavarz, and H. Hecht, “Validating an efficient method to quantify motion sickness,” *Hum Factors*, 53 (4) 415–426 (2011). doi:10.1177/0018720811403736.
 - 25) C.-L.Liu, and S.-T. Uang, “A study of sickness induced within a 3D virtual store and combated with fuzzy control in the elderly,” in: *9th International Conference on Fuzzy Systems and Knowledge*

- Discovery, IEEE, 2012: pp. 334–338. doi:10.1109/FSKD.2012.6234149.
- 26) J.J.LaViola, "A discussion of cybersickness in virtual environments," *ACM SIGCHI Bulletin*, 32 (1) 47–56 (2000). doi:10.1145/333329.333344.
 - 27) A.F.Seay, D.M. Krum, L. Hodges, and W. Ribarsky, "Simulator Sickness and Presence in a High FOV Virtual Environment," in: *Proceeding of the Virtual Reality* (2001): pp. 23-25. doi: 10.1109/VR.2001.913806
 - 28) M.J.Griffin, and N.A. Webb, "Eye movement, vection, and motion sickness with foveal and peripheral vision," *Aviat Space Environ Med*, 74 (6) 622–625 (2003).
 - 29) E.Chang, H.T. Kim, and B. Yoo, "Virtual reality sickness: a review of causes and measurements," *Int J Hum Comput Interact*, 1658–1682 (2020). doi:10.1080/10447318.2020.1778351.
 - 30) E.Chang, I. Hwang, H. Jeon, Y. Chun, H.T. Kim, and C. Park, "Effects of rest frames on cybersickness and oscillatory brain activity," in: *International Winter Workshop on Brain-Computer Interface (BCI)*, IEEE, 2013: pp. 62–64. doi:10.1109/IWW-BCI.2013.6506631.
 - 31) X.Dong, and T.A. Stoffregen, "Postural activity and motion sickness among drivers and passengers in a console video game," in: *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 2010: pp. 1340–1344. doi:10.1518/107118110X12829369835680.
 - 32) X.Dong, K. Yoshida, and T.A. Stoffregen, "Control of a virtual vehicle influences postural activity and motion sickness.," *J Exp Psychol Appl*, 17 (2) 128–138 (2011). doi:10.1037/a0024097.
 - 33) S.J.Villard, M.B. Flanagan, G.M. Albanese, and T.A. Stoffregen, "Postural instability and motion sickness in a virtual moving room," *Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 50 (2) 332–345 (2008). doi:10.1518/001872008X250728.
 - 34) T.A.Stoffregen, K. Yoshida, S. Villard, L. Scibora, and B.G. Bardy, "Stance width influences postural stability and motion sickness," *Ecological Psychology*, 22 (3) 169–191 (2010). doi:10.1080/10407413.2010.496645.
 - 35) S.Davis, K. Nesbitt, and E. Nalivaiko, "Systematic review of cybersickness," in: *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, Association for Computing Machinery, 2014. doi:10.1145/2677758.2677780.
 - 36) S.Davis, K. Nesbitt, and E. Nalivaiko, "Comparing the onset of cybersickness using the Oculus Rift and two virtual roller coasters," 2015.
 - 37) Y.Hu, M. Elwardy, and H.J. Zepernick, "On the effect of standing and seated viewing of 360° videos on subjective quality assessment: a pilot study," *Computers*, 10 (6) (2021). doi:10.3390/computers10060080.
 - 38) N.Tian, P. Lopes, and R. Boulic, "A review of cybersickness in head-mounted displays: raising attention to individual susceptibility," *Virtual Real*, (2022). doi:10.1007/s10055-022-00638-2.
 - 39) R.S.Kennedy, N.E. Lane, K.S. Berbaum, and M.G. Lilienthal, "Simulator sickness questionnaire: an enhanced method for quantifying simulator sickness," *Int J Aviat Psychol*, 3 (3) 203–220 (1993). doi:10.1207/s15327108ijap0303_3.
 - 40) D.Risi, and S. Palmisano, "Effects of postural stability, active control, exposure duration and repeated exposures on hmd induced cybersickness," *Displays*, 60 9–17 (2019). doi:10.1016/j.displa.2019.08.003.
 - 41) J.Clifton, and S. Palmisano, "Effects of steering locomotion and teleporting on cybersickness and presence in hmd-based virtual reality," *Virtual Real*, 24 (3) 453–468 (2020). doi:10.1007/s10055-019-00407-8.
 - 42) da Silva Marinho, U. Terton, and C.M. Jones, "Cybersickness and postural stability of first time vr users playing vr videogames," *Appl Ergon*, 101 (2022). doi:10.1016/j.apergo.2022.103698.
 - 43) A.M.Gavani, K. V. Nesbitt, K.L. Blackmore, and E. Nalivaiko, "Profiling subjective symptoms and autonomic changes associated with cybersickness," *Auton Neurosci*, 203 41–50 (2017). doi:10.1016/j.autneu.2016.12.004.
 - 44) E.Chang, H.T. Kim, and B. Yoo, "Virtual reality sickness: a review of causes and measurements," *Int J Hum Comput Interact*, 1658–1682 (2020). doi:10.1080/10447318.2020.1778351.
 - 45) Y.Y.Kim, H.J. Kim, E.N. Kim, H.D. Ko, and H.T. Kim, "Characteristic changes in the physiological components of cybersickness," *Psychophysiology*, (2005). doi:10.1111/j.1469-8986.2005.00349.x.
 - 46) M.S.Dennison, and M. D'Zmura, "Cybersickness without the wobble: experimental results speak against postural instability theory," *Appl Ergon*, 58 215–223 (2017). doi:10.1016/j.apergo.2016.06.014.
 - 47) T.Magaki, and M. Vallance, "Seeking accessible physiological metrics to detect cybersickness in vr," *International Journal of Virtual and Augmented Reality*, 4 (1) 1–18 (2020). doi:10.4018/ijvar.2020010101.
 - 48) K.Stanney, C. Fidopiastis, and L. Foster, "Virtual reality is sexist: but it does not have to be," *Front Robot AI*, 7 (2020). doi:10.3389/frobt.2020.00004.
 - 49) R.Gilgen-Ammann, T. Schweizer, and T. Wyss, "RR interval signal quality of a heart rate monitor and an ecg holter at rest and during exercise," *Eur J Appl Physiol*, 119 (7) 1525–1532 (2019). doi:10.1007/s00421-019-04142-5.
 - 50) L.Fan, J. Wang, Q. Li, Z. Song, J. Dong, F. Bao, and

- X. Wang, "Eye movement characteristics and visual fatigue assessment of virtual reality games with different interaction modes," *Front Neurosci*, 17 (2023). doi:10.3389/fnins.2023.1173127.
- 51) H. Shigemasa, T. Morita, N. Matsuzaki, T. Sato, M. Harasawa, and K. Aizawa, "Effects of physical display size and amplitude of oscillation on visually induced motion sickness," in: *Proceedings of the ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology - VRST '06*, ACM Press, New York, New York, USA, 2006: p. 372. doi:10.1145/1180495.1180571.
- 52) A. Ozkan, U. Uyan, and U. Celikkan, "Effects of speed, complexity and stereoscopic vr cues on cybersickness examined via eeg and self-reported measures," *Displays*, 78 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.displa.2023.102415.
- 53) A.H.X. Yang, N.K. Kasabov, and Y.O. Cakmak, "Prediction and detection of virtual reality induced cybersickness: a spiking neural network approach using spatiotemporal eeg brain data and heart rate variability," *Brain Inform*, 10 (1) (2023). doi:10.1186/s40708-023-00192-w.
- 54) J.R. Park, D.W. Lim, S.Y. Lee, H.W. Lee, M.H. Choi, and S.C. Chung, "Long-term study of simulator sickness: differences in EEG response due to individual sensitivity," *International Journal of Neuroscience*, 118 (6) 857–865 (2008). doi:10.1080/00207450701239459.
- 55) Thomas Alsop, "Virtual reality (vr) headworn device sales worldwide from 2021 to 2024," *Statista*, (2021).
- 56) J.F. Golding, K. Doolan, A. Acharya, M. Tribak, and M.A. Gresty, "Cognitive cues and visually induced motion sickness," *Aviat Space Environ Med*, 83 (5) 477–482 (2012). doi:10.3357/ASEM.3095.2012.
- 57) K. Stanney, B.D. Lawson, B. Rokers, M. Dennison, C. Fidopiastis, T. Stoffregen, S. Weech, and J.M. Fulvio, "Identifying causes of and solutions for cybersickness in immersive technology: reformulation of a research and development agenda," *Int J Hum Comput Interact*, 36 (19) 1783–1803 (2020). doi:10.1080/10447318.2020.1828535.
- 58) G. Gonçalves, "Virtual Reality Games: a study about the level of interaction vs. narrative and the gender in presence and cybersickness," in: *International Conference on Graphics and Interaction*, IEEE, 2018: pp. 1-8. doi: 10.1109/ITCGI.2018.8602686.
- 59) T. Luong, A. Plechata, M. Mobus, M. Atchapero, R. Bohm, G. Makransky, and C. Holz, "Demographic and Behavioral Correlates of Cybersickness," in: *IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality*, ISMAR: pp. 307–316. doi:10.1109/ISMAR55827.2022.00046.
- 60) K.M.T. Pöhlmann, G. Li, M. McGill, F. Pollick, and S. Brewster, "Can Gender and Motion Sickness Susceptibility Predict Cybersickness in VR?," in: *IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)*, IEEE, 2023: pp. 277–282. doi:10.1109/VRW58643.2023.00066.
- 61) J. Zhang, X. Che, E. Chang, C. Qu, X. Di, H. Liu, and J. Su, "How different text display patterns affect cybersickness in augmented reality," *Sci Rep*, 14 (1) (2024). doi:10.1038/s41598-024-62338-y.
- 62) N. Tian, and R. Boulic, "The least increasing aversion (lia) protocol: illustration on identifying individual susceptibility to cybersickness triggers," *IEEE Trans Vis Comput Graph*, (2024). doi:10.1109/TVCG.2024.3395365.
- 63) D.R. Lampton, E.M. Kolasinski, B.W. Knerr, J.P. Bliss, J.H. Bailey, and B.G. Witmer, "Side Effect And Aftereffects Of Immersion In Virtual Environments," in: *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 1994: pp. 1154–1157. doi: 10.1177/154193129403801802.
- 64) J. Hakkinen, T. Vuori, and M. Paakka, "Postural stability and sickness symptoms after HMD use," in: *IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics*, IEEE, 2002: pp. 147–152. doi:10.1109/ICSMC.2002.1167964.
- 65) S.A. Clemes, and P.A. Howarth, "The menstrual cycle and susceptibility to virtual simulation sickness," *J Biol Rhythms*, 20 (1) 71–82 (2005). doi:10.1177/0748730404272567.
- 66) K. Stanney, C. Fidopiastis, and L. Foster, "Virtual reality is sexist: but it does not have to be," *Front Robot AI*, 7 (2020). doi:10.3389/frobt.2020.00004.
- 67) R.R. Mourant, and T.R. Thattacheny, "Simulator Sickness In A Virtual Environments Driving Simulator," in: *Proceedings Of The IEA HFES Congress*, 2000: pp. 534–537.
- 68) M.M. Knight, and L.L. Arns, "The Relationship Among Age and Other Factors on Incidence of Cybersickness in Immersive Environment Users," in: *APGV*, 2006. doi: 10.1145/1179622.1179846
- 69) M. Melo, J. Vasconcelos-Raposo, and M. Bessa, "Presence and cybersickness in immersive content: effects of content type, exposure time and gender," *Computers and Graphics*, 71 159–165 (2018). doi:10.1016/j.cag.2017.11.007.
- 70) C. Zhou, C.L. Bryan, E. Wang, N.S. Artan, and Z. Dong, "Cognitive Distraction to Improve Cybersickness in Virtual Reality Environment," in: *16th International Conference on Mobile Ad Hoc and Smart Systems Workshops*, MASSW., 2019: pp. 72–76. doi:10.1109/MASSW.2019.00021.
- 71) C. Curry, R. Li, N. Peterson, and T.A. Stoffregen, "Cybersickness in virtual reality head-mounted displays: examining the influence of sex differences and vehicle control," *Int J Hum Comput Interact*, 36

- (12) 1161–1167 (2020). doi:10.1080/10447318.2020.1726108.
- 72) S. Weech, T. Wall, and M. Barnett-Cowan, "Reduction of cybersickness during and immediately following noisy galvanic vestibular stimulation," *Exp Brain Res*, 238 (2) 427–437 (2020). doi:10.1007/s00221-019-05718-5.
- 73) A. Hendrika, C. Theresia, and T. Yogasara, "Cybersickness testing of gender and experience factors using virtual reality," *International Journal of Engineering*, 2 (2) 2685–3191 (2020). doi:10.46923/ijets.v2i2.79
- 74) C. Sagnier, E. Loup-Escande, and G. Valléry, "Effects of gender and prior experience in immersive user experience with virtual reality," in: *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, Springer Verlag, 2020: pp. 305–314. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-19135-1_30.
- 75) J.F. Golding, "Motion sickness susceptibility," *Auton Neurosci*, 129 (1–2) 67–76 (2006). doi:10.1016/j.autneu.2006.07.019.
- 76) P. Kourtesis, R. Amir, J. Linnell, F. Argelaguet, and S.E. MacPherson, "Cybersickness, cognition, & motor skills: the effects of music, gender, and gaming experience," *IEEE Trans Vis Comput Graph*, (2023). doi:10.1109/TVCG.2023.3247062.
- 77) G.D. Park, R.W. Allen, D. Fiorentino, T.J. Rosenthal, and M.L. Cook, "Simulator sickness scores according to symptom susceptibility, age, and gender for an older driver assessment study," in: *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, 50 (26) 2702–2706 (2006). doi:10.1177/154193120605002607.
- 78) L. Rebenitsch, and C. Owen, "Individual variation in susceptibility to cybersickness," in: *Proceedings of the 27th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology*, Association for Computing Machinery, 2014: pp. 309–318. doi:10.1145/2642918.2647394.
- 79) L.L. Arns, and M.M. Cerney, "The Relationship Between Age and Incidence of Cybersickness Among Immersive Environment Users," in: *Proceedings of the IEEE Virtual Reality*, 2005: pp. 267–268. doi:10.1109/VR.2005.1492788.
- 80) J.O. Brooks, R.R. Goodenough, M.C. Crisler, N.D. Klein, R.L. Alley, B.L. Koon, W.C. Logan, J.H. Ogle, R.A. Tyrrell, and R.F. Wills, "Simulator sickness during driving simulation studies," *Accid Anal Prev*, 42 (3) 788–796 (2010). doi:10.1016/j.aap.2009.04.013.
- 81) X. Liu, Y. Liu, X. Zhu, M. An, and F. Hu, "Virtual reality based navigation training for astronaut moving in a simulated space station," in: *VAMR* Springer Verlag, 2016: pp. 416–423. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-39907-2_40.
- 82) J. Hildebrandt, P. Schmitz, A. Calero Valdez, L. Kobbelt, and M. Ziefle, "Get Well Soon! Human Factors' Influence on Cybersickness after Redirected Walking Exposure in Virtual Reality," in: *Virtual, Augmented and Mixed Reality: Interaction, Navigation, Visualization, Embodiment, and Simulation*, 2018: pp. 1–20. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-91581-4_7.
- 83) B. Keshavarz, H. Hecht, and L. Zschuschke, "Intra-visual conflict in visually induced motion sickness," *Displays*, 32 (4) 181–188 (2011). doi:10.1016/j.displa.2011.05.009.
- 84) K. Petri, K. Feuerstein, S. Folster, F. Bariszlovich, and K. Witte, "Effects of age, gender, familiarity with the content, and exposure time on cybersickness in immersive head-mounted display based virtual reality," *Am J Biomed Sci*, 107–121 (2020). doi:10.5099/aj200200107.
- 85) L. Tychsen, and P. Foeller, "Effects of immersive virtual reality headset viewing on young children: visuomotor function, postural stability, and motion sickness," *Am J Ophthalmol*, 209 151–159 (2020). doi:10.1016/j.ajo.2019.07.020.
- 86) D. Saredakis, A. Szpak, B. Birkhead, H.A.D. Keage, A. Rizzo, and T. Loetscher, "Factors associated with virtual reality sickness in head-mounted displays: a systematic review and meta-analysis," *Front Hum Neurosci*, 14 (2020). doi:10.3389/fnhum.2020.00096.
- 87) T. Goodge, V. Kroll, M. Vernon, P. Ventsislavova, and D. Crundall, "A comparison of cybersickness symptoms across 360-degree hazard perception and hazard prediction tests for drivers," *Appl Ergon*, 97 (2021). doi:10.1016/j.apergo.2021.103549.
- 88) A. Jasper, N.C. Sepich, S.B. Gilbert, J.W. Kelly, and M.C. Dorneich, "Predicting cybersickness using individual and task characteristics," *Comput Human Behav*, 146 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.chb.2023.107800.
- 89) M.P. Séba, P. Maillot, S. Hanne-ton, and G. Dietrich, "Influence of normal aging and multisensory data fusion on cybersickness and postural adaptation in immersive virtual reality," *Sensors*, 23 (23) (2023). doi:10.3390/s23239414.
- 90) K. Kim, M.Z. Rosenthal, D.J. Zielinski, and R. Brady, "Effects of virtual environment platforms on emotional responses," *Comput Methods Programs Biomed*, 113 (3) 882–893 (2014). doi:10.1016/j.cmpb.2013.12.024.
- 91) A. Paroz, and L.E. Potter, "Impact of air flow and a hybrid locomotion system on cybersickness," in: *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, Association for Computing Machinery, 2018: pp. 582–586. doi:10.1145/3292147.3292229.
- 92) I.M. Arafat, S.M.S. Ferdous, and J. Quarles, "The effects of cybersickness on persons with multiple sclerosis," in: *Proceedings of the ACM Symposium*

- on Virtual Reality Software and Technology, VRST, Association for Computing Machinery, 2016: pp. 51–59. doi:10.1145/2993369.2993383.
- 93) E.Chang, H.T. Kim, and B. Yoo, “Predicting cybersickness based on user’s gaze behaviors in hmd-based virtual reality,” *J Comput Des Eng*, 8 (2) 728–739 (2021). doi:10.1093/jcde/qwab010.
 - 94) Olwin, Y.Christian, “Virtual reality cybersickness analysis of myopy and presbiopy users: a study of user perception,” *Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science (INTECOMS)*, 6 (1) (2023). doi: 10.31539/intecom.v6i1.5839
 - 95) M.Pau, F. Aripa, B. Leban, M. Porta, G. Casu, J. Frau, L. Loreface, G. Coghe, and E. Cocco, “Cybersickness in people with multiple sclerosis exposed to immersive virtual reality,” *Bioengineering*, 11 (2) (2024). doi:10.3390/bioengineering11020115.
 - 96) Brion M. Silva, and Pumudu Fernando, “Early Prediction of Cybersickness in Virtual, Augmented & Mixed Reality Applications: A Review,” in *5th International Conference for Convergence in Technology (I2CT).*, IEEE, 2019. doi: 10.1109/I2CT45611.2019.9033650.
 - 97) K.S.Kingdon, K.M. Stanney, and R.S. Kennedy, “Extreme responses to virtual environment exposure,” in: *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, pp 1906–1910 2001. doi:10.1177/154193120104502711.
 - 98) S.Klosterhalfen, S. Kellermann, U. Stockhorst, G. Hall, and P. Enck, “Effects of ethnicity and gender on motion sickness susceptibility,” *Aviat Space Environ Med*, 76 (11) (2005).
 - 99) Y.Wang, J.-R. Chardonnet, F. Merienne, and J. Ovtcharova, “Using Fuzzy Logic to Involve Individual Differences for Predicting Cybersickness during VR Navigation,” in: *Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*, IEEE, 2021: pp. 373–381. doi:10.1109/VR50410.2021.00060.
 - 100) T.A.Stoffregen, and L.J. Smart, “Postural instability precedes motion sickness,” *Brain Research Bulletin*, 47 (5) (1999). doi: 10.1016/S0361-9230(98)00102-6.
 - 101) J.Munafo, M. Diedrick, and T.A. Stoffregen, “The virtual reality head-mounted display oculus rift induces motion sickness and is sexist in its effects,” *Exp Brain Res*, 235 (3) 889–901 (2017). doi:10.1007/s00221-016-4846-7.
 - 102) E.Faugloire, C.T. Bonnet, M.A. Riley, B.G. Bardy, and T.A. Stoffregen, “Motion sickness, body movement, and claustrophobia during passive restraint,” *Exp Brain Res*, 177 (4) 520–532 (2007). doi:10.1007/s00221-006-0700-7.
 - 103) R.Kennedy, K.M. Stanney, and W.P. Dunlap, “Duration and exposure to virtual environments: sickness curves during and across sessions,” *Presence*, 463–472 (2000). doi: 10.1162/105474600566952.
 - 104) B.W.Stone III, A. Froelich, M. Credé, J. Kelly, and Z. Krizan, “Psychometric evaluation of the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire as a measure of cybersickness,” Iowa State University, 2017.
 - 105) R.Islam, Y. Lee, M. Jaloli, I. Muhammad, D. Zhu, and J. Quarles, “Automatic Detection of Cybersickness from Physiological Signal in a Virtual Roller Coaster Simulation,” in: *Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces, VRW*, 2020: pp. 649–650. doi:10.1109/VRW50115.2020.00175.
 - 106) A.Kim, J.E. Lee, and K.M. Lee, “An Investigation on the Relationship between Cybersickness and Heart Rate Variability When Navigating a Virtual Environment,” in: *International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality Adjunct, ISMAR*, 2022: pp. 794–797. doi:10.1109/ISMAR-Adjunct57072.2022.00169.
 - 107) J.Sameri, H. Coenegracht, S. Van Damme, F. De Turck, and M. Torres Vega, “Physiology-driven cybersickness detection in virtual reality: a machine learning and explainable ai approach,” *Virtual Real*, 28 (4) (2024). doi:10.1007/s10055-024-01067-z.
 - 108) T.Goodge, V. Kroll, M. Vernon, P. Ventsislavova, and D. Crundall, “A comparison of cybersickness symptoms across 360-degree hazard perception and hazard prediction tests for drivers,” *Appl Ergon*, 97 (2021). doi:10.1016/j.apergo.2021.103549.